

PRODUCTIVE STRUCTURE AND SPATIAL INEQUALITIES: THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE CLUSTERS

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the interactions among socio-economic inequalities and the spaces they concern, investigating the connections between economic production, social capital and inequality in a region. Main research questions are about the spatial relations between the demand side of labour market and multidimensional inequality, especially looking at the role of innovative clusters. The production structure and social capital endowments of 205 selected EU15 regions have been reviewed for the time range 2000-2011. Available data have been synthesised by explorative Principal Component Analysis. Extracted indicators for the two selected economic and social dimensions have been compared to the levels of the estimated multidimensional measure of inequality in the regions. Results say that spatial distributions of considered domains share similar patterns, opposing north to south of Europe.

Keywords: Clusters, Europe, Inequality, Region, Social-Capital.

1. INTRODUCTION:

A theory of territorial inequality does not exist as such, but in the wide range of spatial approaches to territorial analysis, valuable contributions to this research field have been produced by many economists, sociologists, and geographers among others. These complementary approaches have, however, rarely been combined in regional studies. One aim of this piece of research is to contribute to fill this gap, drawing from several theoretical references and bringing together their separate objects of analysis in a multidisciplinary approach to the study of territorial inequality. The final goal is to produce a multidimensional analysis of socio-economic inequalities based on different regional traits. Specific focuses are business structure and production clusters' specialisation, along with levels of social capital. The definition of clusters assumed in this article refers to the concept of agglomeration of firms, and especially to the extensive research carried out by the Center for Strategy and Competitiveness (CSC) at the Stockholm School of Economics and the European Cluster Observatory (Sölvell et al., 2007; Ketels, Protsiv, 2013). Due to the several approaches available for the measurement of inequality itself, it is worth clarifying also that the inequality here used is defined as inequality of outcomes, specifically with regards to the multidimensional framework of human development economics and capability approach.

Main questions to be answered in this paper are then the following: how EU15 regions position themselves with respect to multidimensional inequality when it comes to the interaction among production structure and social endowments? what is the role of innovative business clusters in respect to these spatial distributions? In the search for the answers, an overarching assumption implies that the economic engines of inequality are not enough to explain its trends. Some other aspect such as spatial, cultural and social elements has to be taken into consideration, together, so to identify the latent factors in these complex dynamics. In order to get a complete picture and a better understanding of the relationship between man,

community and space, and how to study their joint development (eventually unequal), considering the spatial context seems vital. The relations in place between the considered dynamics of regional development, based on economic production and specialisation, have not been totally clarified yet- not with specific attention to their implications in terms of innovation and social inclusiveness either. The exercise here proposed tries to find other evidence of the spatial disparities in their interactions. Drawing on the mentioned strands of literature and available databases for the EU Member States, 205 regions have been considered over the period from 2000 to 2011. Statistics about regional production clusters and social capital endowments have been reduced to synthetic indicators by applying a Principal Component Analysis. Results have been mapped together with the level of multidimensional inequality, in order to explore their spatial distribution.

This paper is then structured as follows: next section reflects on the importance of considering the spatial dimension in the study of inequality; the third section provides a brief overview of the relevant contributions in the literature about regional disparities in Europe, focusing on the role of social capital and production clusters; the fourth section explains data and methodology applied in the analysis carried out; the fifth section discusses the results of this explorative study; and the last one introduces some preliminary conclusions.

2. WHY SPACE MATTERS IN THE INEQUALITY ANALYSIS

The Oxford Dictionary of Human Geography defines *spatial inequality* as “the geographical expression of social inequality, recognising that space is both the medium and outcome of social relations” (2013). Inequality means also spatial disparity, and this is so because each territory has a set of geographic, social, cultural, institutional and human resources that constitutes the space of its own set of resources and potential for development at the same time. Disparities exist also because socio-economic and policy dynamics of regions and cities are different from each other, and often they are particular to a specific geographic area: that is the reason why the spatial dimension has to be considered when studying inequality (OECD, 2016). Generally speaking, inequality is a matter of uneven distribution of resources among members of a certain community, and that is why it has always been a topic of interest for scholars of distribution theory indeed, within both economics and sociology.

About the multidimensional inequality assumed in this article, it is defined as inequality of outcomes, and it relates mainly to what has been extensively wrote about it by Amartya Sen and Anthony Atkinson. Sen is the main representatives of the *capability approach* in the frame of the human development economics, which has had the remarkable merit of driving the crucial shift “beyond GDP” in economic development studies. It is an intrinsically multidimensional approach that focuses on people and their empowerment in an all-round process of development throughout their lives within the society (about the approach and its operationalisation has been further developed by Alkire, Deneulin, et al. at UNDP). Atkinson has been one of the most prominent scholars of economics of inequality in Europe. He dealt with technical issues of measurement, but also with the definition of inequality and some specific aspects about the labour market mechanisms- notably wage inequality and top income shares (1983, 2007, 2013). His contribution is here relevant also because, even if still in the framework of income inequality studies, he addressed the importance of a multidimensional approach when dealing with distributive justice issues (1983). Clarifying this is important in order to frame the way it has been here measured either development or inequality: focusing on outcome instead than input variables. Attention has so been given to

individuals and their well-being, focusing on personal distribution of achievements. But importance is recognised to the spatial context too, because people's life and their *capabilities* are influenced also by the space they live in.

Specifically looking at the European case, regional studies in all of the above mentioned disciplines have variously contributed to the analysis of disparities between regions of the Union. Stress has been alternatively placed on innovation, geography, institutions, labour market dynamics, business clusters, and so on. Economists are usually more concerned with income inequalities or GDP growth rate differentials, looking at convergence processes between regions and the decomposition of these trends. Sociologists are instead more prone to consider the local processes in terms of territorial systems triggered by –or coming up with– social ties and collaborative activities. Geographers have generally dealt with the spatial dynamics of agglomeration and localisation choice's process. Although such a variety of approaches contributes to improve our understanding of the persistence of inequalities in several domains, along with some of its possible drivers, there has been limited mutual enrichment between these different, but nevertheless complementary strands of literature. Finally, a comprehensive picture of the specific relationships between economic cluster policies and human development across European regions is still missing.

Thinking about all of the possible ways that well-being and its dimensions can be related, it appears clear that many different domains contribute to the level of (unequal) development, and also that they are all related to each other. One way to tackle the analysis is restricting the focus to the employment dimension only. And this is at least for two reasons. First, employment is acknowledged by all theories as one of the main domains enabling people to actively participate in the society and so to realise their aspirations. Second, at the same time the labour market is the main place where different kinds of inequality involving several domains take place and reinforce themselves (of course wage inequalities, but also educational and gender inequality can be faced there). Moreover, here policy interventions can have a substantial as well as immediate impact. Most of the inequality studies dealing with labour market structure and its functionings often focus on the labour supply side only, investigating wage inequalities and top income shares, investments in human capital and returns to education, welfare institutions and workers, just to name a few examples. A lot has been written about how the labour force performs, how it allocates and relocates, how it is employed and rewarded. Plenty has been published even on the mechanisms governing social networks, or the intergenerational transmission of wage inequality (Atkinson, 2007, 2013). Less has been studied about the influence of the labour demand side on different sorts of inequalities. Furthermore, even if Atkinson himself focused more on the labour supply, he recognised the importance of looking at the demand side in order to fill our gaps in knowledge about the economic inequality mechanisms (Atkinson, 1983).

Especially, when it comes to territorial inequalities, the studies focusing on regional employment and production structures are still intrigued mostly by the possible ways for boosting growth towards regional convergence, rather than jointly considering some other related social implications. In addition, the EU regional Cohesion Policy is always more concerned with innovative clusters, as a good way of boosting growth and promoting local development (2014). Can we say these growth spill-overs are actually inclusive though? Based on this, regions are called on always more attention to locally established strong specialisation and innovations, and may be classified in leaders and followers according to their innovation pace (Regional Innovation Scoreboard, 2014). But what about the effects on the multidimensional inequalities in the regions these industries are located in? If we agree

that territories are made of people and they are the last recipients of any policy intervention in the end, the development of a territory can be considered equitable or not based on the implications for citizens' well-being. Finally, inequalities between territories may mean inequality of opportunities for their inhabitants, which may lead to low social mobility: too often socio-economic issues are faced without taking into account their territorial aspects, while the consideration of the spatial context may be crucial for a correct analysis.

3. UNEQUAL DEVELOPMENT, CLUSTERS AND SOCIAL CAPITAL

Spatially contextualising this study at a subnational scale is important because a local system is probably the best territorial unit of analysis to gather and practice new policies, as well as the one where human and social capital are more likely to emerge as driving forces of development. There is evidence that the real engines of world's economy are still established at the local level. And since the localisation of people and activities determines nature and quality of our lives, in recent decades local development has become a central issue in both the national public policy and the international development cooperation (Glaeser, 2003).

Historically, localisation choices have variously been analysed by economic theory, especially with respect to agglomeration dynamics and related externalities. From the first models of localisation theory, through those of regional growth, to the more recent local development ones, the mechanisms locally determined by proximity, complementarity or functionality factors have always interested economists and geographers (Capello, 2004). The spatial diffusion of economic development can indeed produce amazingly beneficial spin-offs, but also powerful agglomeration diseconomies that hold back and eventually stop the growth of poles (Prager, Thisse, 2012). The specificity of the last theories is the strong spatial feature of development, which is affected and reinforced itself by the connection to a specific territory. Furthermore, high importance is given to intangible elements, such as knowledge exchange, know-how, social and institutional relations. These characteristics seemed more likely to occur within regional economic systems, and -when present- to be as well the main reason of the local economies resilience to possible external shocks.

In the frame of regional studies' spatial analysis, the role of firms' clusters as engines of development has therefore become relevant. Different approaches have been elaborated, and their impact on growth and regional progress further studied (Porter 2003, 2013; Becattini, 1990, 2000; Boschma, 2014). Dating back to Alfred Marshall (1890, 1921), the social characteristics and business environment –i.e. the territorial milieu- typical of areas where geographic concentration of production activities occur was clear. Since then, it has been approached and analysed in depth by different point of views, and it became central again during the 90s, after Porter's and Krugman's works (1990, 1991). Object of the study has come to be the relation between presence of clusters and local (and national) economic performance, and the positive association between the two has been emphasised.

One aspect that is still mostly unclear is the trigger for a favourable environment to turn into a successful cluster location. And here the local endowments of social capital come into play: their importance as driver of the performance difference across locations has been increasingly recognised (Rodriguez-Pose, Crescenzi, 2008). Social capital is a complex concept, for which several definitions have been developed. It can include a variety of elements, such as the level of trust (Fukuyama, 1995); the civic involvement and participation of citizens (Putnam, 1993); and different kinds of social relations (Bourdieu, 1986; Coleman,

1988). In the end, all of these aspects have an impact on either the public or private actors, both at the individual and collective level, and eventually seem to make it more likely that “mere co-location is leveraged through active collaboration and that beneficial local conditions are strengthened through coordinated or joint action” (Ketels, Protsiv, 2013). Furthermore, as Rodriguez-Pose wrote years ago about the role of “local social structures” in explaining the persistence of regional disparities in Europe (1998): the existing social conditions may play an essential role in an area’s receptivity to -and assimilation of- technological change and economic processes.

Looking more closely at social endowments of regions and their relation with local economic structure, an interesting more recent piece of research by Boschma et al. (2016) tries to infer the role of different kinds of social capital (and of quality of institutions) on regional diversification and production specialisation. Drawing on previous work about the different economic payoffs of either bridging or bonding social capital by Knack and Keefer (1997) and Beugelsdijk et al. (2005, 2009), they analyse the role of informal institutions in more than one hundred European regions from 2004 to 2012. First of all, they find the relatedness of regional specialisations to be positively linked to existing strong industries in the region. Second of all, they show that informal institutions have a big play in this development path, and that bridging social capital is a key driver for regional diversification with significant levels of “trust and active participation in bridging type of groups increase the probability of regions to diversity into new sectors”. Bonding social capital, instead, seems to have no impact, or even a negative one where the quality of local government is poor.

While being more widely analysed in its (positive) relation to economic growth, social capital has also been studied in its relation to economic inequality, in both directions: what is the effect of different kinds of social capital on the level of inequality? And how does the extent of inequality affect the formation of social capital in a region? Here a generally negative association has been suggested, but the direction of the effects results less clear. Interesting evidence in both sense has been produced by De Blasio and Nuzzo about Italian regions (2005, 2012). They found a significant association between several inequality measures and social capital indicators, highlighting that different social capital definitions may produce different results: the relation is negative in the case of bridging and linking ones, while positive for the bonding networks (which, favouring their members only, may foster the persistence of existing disparities). An interesting aspect is that these associations seem to pass through –and be then more evident in- the labour market. There may be several drivers, which may explain the negative association that goes from low level of social capital (or a bonding one stronger than the bridging/linking ones) to higher level of inequality. These may be, for example, a lower productivity due to professionally unfair behaviour and higher costs borne by firms to counter them; inefficient job-matching because of the prominent use of personal network in the job search; poor propensity to entrepreneurship in an unfavourable business environment; strong family ties that hampers women’s employment. Even on the other side, when inequality is lower, pro-social behaviours are more likely to occur. A broader look at the European situation suggests similar considerations, as emerge from the last Reports on Economic, Social and Territorial Cohesion in the EU (2014). The mutual influence of territorial characteristics and social unrest is stated, highlighting an eroded social capital where inequality is spatially concentrated, along with the need for place-based policies to tackle social exclusion (2010).

When talking about regional disparities and policy interventions tackling them, the EU Cohesion Policy is actually the related tool for European regions. Main objective is stated as

helping less developed regions to catch up and “to reduce the economic, social and territorial disparities that still exist in the EU” (EC, 2014). Recently, it has been always more concerned with innovative industries and their role within place-based Smart Specialisations Strategies (S3). These are currently intended as the mainstream for regional development policy planning, as well as the necessary step to get access to related communitarian funding in Europe (EC, 2015). Further details about S3 and their application to EU Cohesion Policy are provided by McCann., Ortega-Argilés, 2011, and Boschma, Giannelle, 2014).

Finally, some interesting contributions specific to the role of clusters in a sustainable regional growth in the EU have been produced in the direction of a compound approach, aiming at jointly consider different dimensions of analysis and coming up with some policy recommendations. In 2013, Ketels and Protsiv provided background research to the WWWforEurope project. Beside other relevant studies previously produced (INNOVA, 2006), here they have specifically contributed to the evaluation of the role of clusters and cluster-based policies in the overall EU strategy for a New Growth Path (i.e. more sustainable and balanced between economic, social and environmental domains). Drawing on related US literature and evidence framework (Porter, 2003), their goal was to test if European regions where clusters and cluster initiatives are present have better performance in economic, environmental and social outcomes. They found confirmed that average wages are significantly and positively influenced by the presence of clusters in the regions, suggesting that specialisation and industry concentration have a role in lifting economic performance. Specifically looking at the implications also for social and environmental components, they were able to draw six different typologies of regions, based on the combinations between performances in the three domains. A general conclusion is that regions with strong clusters tend to follow a more balanced development path, and so clusters can be considered as an indicator for conditions that contribute to the outcomes of a more sustainable growth, even though not being their root cause. Furthermore, a big effort in these works has been put on establishing a new comprehensive database for European NUTS2 regions with the European Cluster Observatory (launched in 2007), and designing a new Regional Competitiveness Index. This measure is intended to assess “the ability of a region to offer an attractive and sustainable environment for firms and residents to live and work” and so to better summarise the business environments of regions, going beyond the mere economic productivity of their business structures (Dijkstra et al, 2011). These are some of the reasons why production clusters and related social environment are still central in local development, and it so may be of interest to further analyse their role on regional disparities.

4. AN EXPLORATION OF EUROPEAN REGIONS

Data used in this study come from several sources and regional databases. As regards regional inequalities, the main measure here used as proxy for multidimensional inequality is the percentage *loss in human development* due to the inequalities present in the society (Alkire and Foster, 2010) calculated on OECD and Eurostat databases, and EU-SILC survey. Detailed methodology and results from this previous section of the study are not object of this paper, but it is here worth it to mention how this measure has been statistically derived per 205 selected regions: comparing the estimated Human Development Index (HDI) to its adjustment to within-region inequalities (related statistical analysis is part of the work developed within the PhD dissertation this paper relates to as well- and whose conclusions and publishing are forthcoming). Following the related literature and the most recently applied UNDP methodology (HDR, 2016), regional HDIs and Inequality-adjusted Human

Development indices have been calculated over a span of time of twelve years, from 2000 to 2011. The territorial unit of analysis has been set at the Eurostat NUTS2 regions, within the EU15 only and excluding the extra-continental regions (French, Spanish and Portuguese overseas departments). This level of detail has been preferred for at least two reasons: wider and more homogeneous availability of human development variables in the selected span of time for countries of interest; comparability to other regional performance and innovation indicators not available yet at a lower territorial specification. Results say that despite a general increase in the potential human development across regions, the levels of its loss due to inequality have not significantly improved over the selected period. Especially, its spatial distribution reveals complex dynamics, showing an increasing concentration of better performances around some more advanced and educated core regions (e.g. in southern UK and Germany, and around the French and Scandinavian capital cities) and confirming the well-known North-South contrast.

For the same 205 regions, trends of production structure have been here explored. Among the available business structure statistics, the distribution of employment across sectors and industries has been considered, and especially looking at regional diversification and clusters' specialisation. Specific data about forty-one production clusters collected by the European Cluster Observatory are available at the level of detail of 4-digits NACE2 industries per region. Related *Location Quotients* (LQs) help explore some territorial paths of economic production, to discover if a region has developed one or more core industries over time, and in which sector. LQ considers the level of employment in a "x" sector in the selected region compared to the national level in the same sector. If the measure is: lower than 1, that sector is not present in the region; equal to 1, region and country specialised at the same level; higher than 1, the region is specialised; over 2, the region is highly specialised. The local level of social capital endowments refers to some measures from the European Social Survey (2014): the level of inter-human trust, along with two items on the perception of helpfulness and fairness of citizens; also, the rate of participation in voluntary activities implying bridging/bonding networks has been considered. The innovation performance relates to the Regional Innovation Scoreboard by Eurostat (2014). The quality of local institutions has been included as captured by the European Quality of Governance Index (EQI) produced by the Quality of Government Institute (2013). Another predictor, used to spatially characterise these regions and account for geography, is the degree of urbanisation.

The methodology applied in the study here reported draws on the social sciences research methods and is an exploratory factor analysis by Principal Component Analysis method (PCA) (Di Franco, Marradi, 2013). Originally conceived by psychologists and sociologists straddling the 19th and 20th centuries, this method uses multivariate analysis' techniques to synthesise variance of processed variables into a reduced number of factors. Underlying hypothesis is that selected variables have a substantial degree of association and especially share a common semantic meaning. For these reasons, extracted components can be used as synthetic indicators for common latent variables that capture more dense information about them. In this case, it allows to include condensed information on innovative clusters in the analysis aiming at better understanding their possible relation with levels of inequality and other regional characteristics- to be further explored by additional quantitative models. Due to the high number of items available to represent the production structure, drawing on some recent similar application on the Italian case (Gemmiti, Santini, 2016) a PCA has been performed on the clusters LQs database first. This has allowed to construct a synthetic measure summarising main traits of regional production, and reduce the original number of forty-one variables (e.g. the 41 industries' clusters). Moreover, a second PCA has been

separately applied to the five available social capital items referred to above. Results of these applications are presented in the following paragraph, after a brief overview of the interactions between considered variables and levels of estimated inequality.

5. SOME RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As explained in the second paragraph, one underlying assumption is that inequality is influenced by different specialisation paths, and these are related to regional specific characteristics such as the social capital endowments. As the following Charts 1. to 5. show, a first comparison between the previously estimated measure of inequality and the values of selected predictors in the 205 regions reveals that relations in place are not necessarily linear, and some State-effects may also be considerable. Different colours of dots stand for different EU Member States, and vertical and horizontal lines –when present- respectively mark the average levels of indicators either on y- or x- axis.

Chart 1. Trust and Inequality

Chart 2

. Quality of Government and Inequality

Chart 3. Innovation and Inequality

Chart 4. Degree of urbanisation and Inequality

Regions where levels of trust are higher than average (in the upper-left quarter of Chart 1) tend to have lower value of loss in human development. While for those below the average level of trust indicator (in the same Chart 1), the performances in inequality are bad only (they all fall within the right-end side marked by the vertical line). Regions where the quality of local institutions is higher than average (those above the horizontal line in Chart 2), show concentration of multidimensional inequality below its average value (all regions are on the left-end side defined by the vertical line). At the same time, for those below the EQI index average, the pattern is more scattered and a slightly negative correlation emerges, associating

better performances of institutions to lower level of inequality. Still with some probable State-effect different dynamics, a higher level of inequality tends to appear in regions where the performances in terms of innovation are poorer (see Chart 3). Finally, all of this is more or less regardless of the degree of urbanisation, as evident from Chart 4.

As introduced in previous paragraph 4, a PCA has been applied to the clusters database. The first two components extracted reproduce one third of the variance of selected variables together, so are not sufficient to provide a comprehensive picture of the regional business structure alone. But they are already informative on a first interpretation of the ties between the domains object of this work. The components have been interpreted based both on the loading components recorded on each of the 41 clusters, and on the measured correlation to regional characteristics. The first component seems to relate to the degree of diversification of regional business structures and to have a double polarity- opposing industry to services. Its correlation with the count of industries in which regions have LQ values higher than 2 is 60%. The second component pertains more to the business environment features, and has a single polarity probably ranging from low to higher content of innovation- showing a strong correlation with both the Regional Innovation Scoreboard (55%) and the number of patents (43%, when the correlation between these two is 50%). Drawing on this, Chart 5. can be read looking at the combinations of the characteristics of the two components resulting in the plane quarters, and the relative placement of analysed regions.

Chart 5. First two components extracted by PCA on clusters' LQs, 2011

Running the same analysis on each year, and comparing the scores of extracted factorial components at the beginning to the end of the considered period, the variation seems in line with the given interpretation. Plotted data are shown below in Chart 6. and 7. Production diversification looks relatively stable and regions tend to maintain their core industries. Chart 6. shows an almost perfect overlapping of scores in first and last year of the period by the linear correlation shape of the dots cloud. Degree of specialisation and innovation in clusters, instead, have changed generally more over time- even in a relatively short period of twelve years. The pattern in Chart 7. appears more scattered indeed.

Chart 6. First component in 2000 and 2011 Chart 7. Second component in 2000 and 2011

Plotted regional PCA scores (Chart 5.) provide a first picture of the spatial distribution of some production structure characteristics (in 2011), which can be better explored by a map. Figure 1. shows the spatial pattern of the groupings based on the four combinations of first two extracted PCs. In addition, the multidimensional inequality introduced in the previous paragraph can be here visualised by a grid (Fig. 2.). This exercise can allow the search for common typologies to group regions based on their production structure characteristics, and so may serve as a first basis to recognise shared spatial patterns. The adherence to inequality categories (split by distribution's quartiles) appears not to be perfectly exact, but some traits to be further explored (e.g. by means of a Cluster Analysis) can be traced. More unequal regions are those of southern Europe (thicker grid in Fig. 2.), and correspond mainly to territories with low production diversification and weak innovative specialisation (red in Fig. 1.). Regions with lower level of inequality instead (coarser grid in Fig. 2.), generally present higher values of industries' diversification and cluster specialisation (light green in Fig. 1.).

Figure 1. PCA combinations based 4 groupings Figure 2. Addition of inequality-based 4 groupings

Same levels of multidimensional inequality can be looked at in comparison to social capital and quality of government measures. The two extracted PCs for social capital reproduce the whole variance of original five survey items, and clearly pertain to two different traits of social capital: trust and networks. Results confirm the conclusions suggested by the literature. Trust components of social capital, along with the level of fairness and helpfulness themselves, are negatively associated with inequality indices (significantly around -60%) and positively with quality of government measures (69%). Networks' ties are instead controversial. Being generally not much significant (with values either a bit lower or higher than zero), when they are considered in the distinction between bridging (volunteering for

non-profit organisations) or bonding (volunteering for political parties) differences emerge. Once again confirming the aforementioned findings from the literature, the first one is inversely associated with both inequality (around 40% for the income one) and quality of government, while the second one is always directly correlated with it.

Finally, these first matches between production structure and social capital on one side, and with quality of local government on the other, have been mapped. They are shown in Figure 3. and 4. respectively. Distribution of these variables has been split in four groupings by quartiles. Size of the grids goes from thicker to coarser standing for worst to better regional scores, for both indicators. Patterns revealed by the two grids are almost overlapping, and the opposition between northern and southern Europe appears here more evident.

Figure 3. Trust extracted component groupings Figure 4. Quality of Government Index groupings

6. CONCLUSIONS

Literature contributions within several disciplines have suggested and variously investigated the relations between territorial inequalities, production structure and social capital. The work presented in this paper is an exploratory analysis of these possible relations in place at the regional level within the EU. Data here used to characterise the business structures of analysed regions are specifically about the production clusters' presence and specialisation, as collected by the European Cluster Observatory. Information about 41 clusters have been reduced by a PCA, and an exercise on the first two factorials component extracted tells something about the level of clusters' diversification and the innovative specialisation in the regions. Mappings show that there is room for a more in depth analysis of the selected data, since these results give only an intuition of the complex pattern in place between the considered domains over space.

Preliminary findings say that regions with low production diversification and weak innovative specialisation are mainly those of southern Europe, which are at the same time relatively more unequal. Regions with lower level of inequality instead generally present higher values of industries' diversification and cluster specialisation. In addition, a more prominent contrast between north and south appears when introducing social capital into the mappings. In order to better capture the underlying factors of the explored spatial distributions, some further research is needed. Following steps foresee the application of econometric methodologies to estimate quantitative models, using inequality as a dependent

variable and the other listed predictors as explanatory variables. A multiple linear regression, a longitudinal analysis over the twelve years' time (Wooldridge, 2002), and finally a geographically weighted regression (Fotheringham, 2002) are just a few examples useful to better explain the findings and the spatial relations between them.

In the light of the links between production structure, social capital and inequality suggested in the literature, some first hypothesis to be tested suppose that relations between inequality and social capital may be mediated by the interaction with local business environment and specialisation. Especially, different production specialisations allow to foster diverse kinds of social relations and cultural effects. These effects can engender the spatial interactions within the concerned territories, whose degree of urbanisation can be very different. In addition, policies to address land use and infrastructures' asset can have substantial impacts on the overall pattern: lowering or increasing inequalities, depending on the level of inclusiveness and relatedness they can facilitate, and the localisation of different industries they can favour.

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